

Reporting template for completed project funded by the Creative Commons Open Culture Platform Activity Fund

Reporting year: 2023

Name	Dr. Muhammad Imtiaz Subhani & Amber Osman
Country	Pakistan
Project title	Building a sustainable social, technical & legal infrastructure for Open GLAMs in Pakistan; the quantitative analyses for the development of open heritage science for Pakistani heritage.
When did the project take place?	May-December 2023

Give a one paragraph outline of the project

Outline:

This project aimed to establish a comprehensive and sustainable social, technical, and legal infrastructure for Open GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums) in Pakistan, focusing on fostering open heritage science for Pakistani heritage. The initiative has undertaken in-depth analyses to quantify and assess the GLAMs / heritage sites/ heritage institutions, their current state and their accessibility, while identifying their legal frameworks, technological and social infrastructures and also addressing the technological aspects for digitization and preservation. The heritage sites/ heritage institutions / GLAMs were investigated in terms of their counts in each provinces and cities, their types, their location addresses, and their status of accessibility including license types. Further, for quantifying the Pakistan heritage science, a self-administered focused group survey was conducted through deploying eight focused group volunteers. 2000 respondents/ cultural stakeholders (250 respondents through each of eight focused groups) were reached out from all over Pakistan to quantify the several positions of legal, technological and social frameworks pertaining to Pakistan heritage.

This Study found and confirmed 424 heritage sites/ heritage institutions / GLAMs spread in all provinces of Pakistan (Punjab, Sindh, KPK and Baluchistan) including Gilgit-Baltistan and Azad Kashmir where the counts of heritage sites/ heritage institutions / GLAMs in all outlined provinces are 171, 126, 49, 30, 23 and 25 respectively. Study confirmed that the Province of Punjab is thickly populated in terms of the presence of heritage sites. While the other provinces such as Sindh and KPK have a fair presence of heritage sites/ institutions/ GLAMs. This Study further confirms that heritage Galleries and pictures and other descriptions and details are in the public domain at almost all of the GLAMs in Sindh region now under the MoU signed between Creative Commons, Pakistan Chapter and Ministry of Culture, Govt. of Sindh (the snapshot of legal document of signed MoU between the two outlined parties are attached in appendices). While the same heritage Galleries and pictures and other descriptions and details are under the CC BY SA license on the directions of the Federal Ministry of Culture, Govt. of Pakistan. This Study also pitched the technological infrastructure through launching the Dashboard of heritage sites/ institutions/ GLAMs (Beta Version) for the easy, quick and open access of the details of all heritage sites/ institutions/ GLAMs. The beta version of the dashboard can be accessed at <https://xploreopen.org/open-glams-heritage/>. Further, a website for catering all heritage of Pakistan, a web platform (XploreOpen) is also established. The test version of the platform (open glam project) can be accessed at www.xploreopen.org. This project also mapped out all of the heritage sites/ institutions/ GLAMs of Pakistan on the map of Pakistan while using innovative solution padlet.com. This can be accessed at

Give an overview of the main outcomes from the project

Main outcomes:

This project examined the current status of social, technical and legal Infrastructures. Frameworks of open GLAMs of Pakistan and giving fair and data driven findings on the current status of the mentioned infrastructures/ frameworks.

A. Outcomes for social infrastructure and framework:

A.1. Establishment of progressive web presence of heritage sites/ heritage institutions / GLAMs

- As mentioned for catering most of the heritage of Pakistan, a web platform (XploreOpen) is established. This web presence keeps on adding the pictorial details of heritages of the country as received from the stakeholders. The test version of this web platform can be accessed at www.xploreopen.org .

A.2. Establishment of Social media presence of heritage sites/ heritage institutions / GLAMs

- This project has also established the social media presence of the heritage sites/ institutions/ GLAMs of Pakistan that include presence of XploreOpen on Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/exploreopen/>) and twitter (<https://twitter.com/xploreopen>) for the wider reach of the audience.

A.3. Empirical Outcomes:

For addressing and evaluating the empirical findings for social framework, this research based study initially deployed the one sample T-Test to evaluate the main research questions of this study pertaining to social framework. The findings of T-Test, empirically confirms that,

- Heritage sites/ GLAMS (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museum) of Pakistan are NOT well represented at social media to represent Pakistani culture and heritage as $MV= 1.92$ ($MV < TV$) at $t= -27.647$ (findings are significant).
- Heritage sites/ GLAMS (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museum) of Pakistan are NOT well represented on twitter to represent Pakistani culture and heritage as $MV= 2.07$ ($MV < TV$) at $t= -21.721$ (findings are significant).
- Heritage sites/ GLAMS (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museum) of Pakistan are NOT well represented on Facebook to represent Pakistani culture and heritage as $MV= 1.97$ ($MV < TV$) at $t= -24.404$ (findings are significant).
- Heritage sites/ GLAMS (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museum) of Pakistan are NOT well represented at LinkedIn to represent Pakistani culture and heritage as $MV= 2.05$ ($MV < TV$) at $t= -21.660$ (findings are significant).
- Social media campaigns can significantly promote the cultural and heritage of Pakistan as $MV= 4.19$ ($MV > TV$) at $t= 28.970$ (findings are significant).
- Television can raise awareness and promote cultural heritage through reporting and storytelling as $MV= 4.27$ ($MV > TV$) at $t= 31.687$ (findings are significant).
- Online platforms can raise awareness and promote cultural heritage through reporting and storytelling as $MV=$

4.30 (MV>TV) at $t= 35.782$ (findings are significant).

The outlined proxies of social framework are further investigated through Kendall's correlation test and OLS to evaluate the nexus between the Social media campaigns that promote the cultural and heritage of Pakistan and the rest of proxies of technological framework to understand the importance of Social media campaigns for GLAMs/ heritage sites. The findings of Kendall's correlation test and OLS confirmed that:

- Social media campaigns for promoting cultural and heritage of Pakistan and Television platforms for raising awareness on cultural heritage are 24.5% positively associated with each other at $p= 0.005<0.05$ (findings are significant).
- Social media campaigns for promoting cultural and heritage of Pakistan and other online platforms (webinars etc.) for raising awareness on cultural heritage are 19.4% positively associated with each other at $p= 0.005<0.05$ (findings are significant).
- Social media campaigns for promoting cultural and heritage of Pakistan and exhibitions for promoting cultural heritage are 25.6% associated positively with each other at $p= 0.005<0.05$ (findings are significant).
- Social media campaigns for promoting cultural and heritage of Pakistan significantly positively impacts 24.6% to the Television platforms for raising awareness on cultural heritage, 14.2 % to other online platforms (webinars etc.) for raising awareness on cultural heritage and 27.3% to exhibitions initiatives for Promoting cultural heritage at $p= 0.005<0.05$ (findings are significant).

Precisely, Social media campaign matters for increasing television programs, webinars and exhibitions on heritage awareness and their promotions.

B. Outcomes for technological infrastructure and framework:

B.1. Establishment of digital dashboard (Beta Version) for heritage sites/ heritage institutions / GLAMs

- This project has managed to establish a digital dashboard (Beta Version) for heritage sites/ heritage institutions / GLAMs for the easy, quick and open access of the details of all heritage sites/ institutions/ GLAMs. The beta version of the dashboard can be access at <https://xploreopen.org/open-glams-heritage/>.

B.2. Establishment of Mapping of heritage sites/ heritage institutions / GLAMs

- This project also mapped out all of the heritage sites/ institutions/ GLAMs of Pakistan on the map of Pakistan while using innovative solution padlet.com. This can be accessed at <https://padlet.com/ccpakchap/glams-pakistan-e6zwd2c5a1yphgft>.

B.3. Empirical Outcomes:

For addressing the empirical outcomes of technological framework, this research based study initially employed the one sample T-Test to evaluate the main research questions of this study. The findings of T-Test, empirically confirms that,

- Pakistani Heritage sites have NO significant digitized content on site mostly at $MV= 4.61$ (MV>TV); $t= 40.784$ (findings are significant).

- Pakistani GLAMs are NOT efficiently digitized that can represent Pakistani Culture and Heritage at MV= 4.44 (MV>TV); t= 33.850 (findings are significant).
- Heritage institutions are NOT efficiently engaged in digitizing rare and valuable cultural heritage materials, making them accessible to a global audience as MV= 4.45 (MV>TV) at t= 36.755 (findings are significant).
- Robust and advanced technical infrastructure is significantly essential for the successful operation of the GLAMs sector in Pakistan as MV= 4.50 (MV>TV) at t= 37.862 (findings are significant).
- Improvements in technical infrastructure significantly positively impacts the heritage sector's growth and accessibility as MV= 4.49 (MV>TV) at t= 39.087 (findings are significant).
- The supply chain network within the GLAMs/ open GLAM sector in Pakistan is responsible significantly for the flow of cultural and artistic assets from creators to end-users as MV= 4.40 (MV>TV) at t= 30.535 (findings are significant).
- If a digital dashboard designed for the Pakistani GLAM / heritage sector, it may have the potential to streamline the supply chain network and improve the availability of cultural assets to the public as MV= 4.35 (MV>TV); t= 30.190 (findings are significant).
- Supply chain network is a crucial component in ensuring the efficient flow of cultural and artistic assets within the GLAM sector in Pakistan as MV= 4.44 (MV>TV) at t= 32.646 (findings are significant).
- Significant challenges or bottlenecks within the existing supply chain network for GLAMs in Pakistan, potentially impacting the sector's accessibility and sustainability as MV= 4.36 (MV>TV) at t= 29.935 (findings are significant).
- Inventory Management is Poor in Pakistani GLAMs/ Heritage sites/ Institutions as MV= 3.77 (MV>TV) at t= 11.828 (findings are significant).

The outlined proxies of technological frameworks are further investigated through Kendall's correlation and OLS tests to evaluate the nexus between the digital dashboard presence for the Pakistani GLAMs / heritage sector and the rest of proxies of technological framework to understand the importance of digital dashboard for GLAMs/ heritage sites. The findings of Kendall's correlation test and OLS confirmed that:

- The presence of a digital dashboard for the Pakistani GLAM / heritage sector can be 37.6% significantly positively associated with successful operation of the GLAMs/ heritage sector in Pakistan and 24.9% with heritage sector's growth and accessibility at $p= 0.005 < 0.05$ (findings are significant).
- The presence of a digital dashboard for the Pakistani GLAM / heritage sector may 34% significantly positively impact the successful operation of the GLAMs/ heritage sector in Pakistan and 20.6% to heritage sector's growth and accessibility at $p= 0.005 < 0.05$ (findings are significant).

PS: The digital dashboard for open GLAMs and heritage of Pakistan has been established after keeping in mind the above two findings of Kendall's correlation and OLS tests.

C. Outcomes for legal infrastructure and framework:

C.1. Legal MoU between Creative Commons, Pak Chapter & Ministry of Culture, Govt. of Sindh

- This project has also managed to establish a legal MoU between Creative Commons, Pakistan Chapter and Ministry of Culture, Govt. of Sindh (the snapshot of legal documents of signed MoU between the two outlined parties are attached in appendices).

C.2. Empirical Outcomes:

For addressing the legal framework, this research based project initially employed the one sample T-Test to evaluate the main research questions of this study. The findings of T-Test, empirically confirms that,

- The legal frameworks and regulations for Heritage sites/ heritage institutions / GLAMs are in place to safeguard and protect the diverse heritage culture of Pakistan significantly as $MV= 4.22$ ($MV>TV$) at $t= 17.045$ (findings are significant).
- The Ministry of Culture (both at federal and provincial levels) collaborates with other government bodies to enforce heritage culture preservation laws effectively and significantly, as $MV= 3.64$ ($MV>TV$) at $t= 8.094$ (findings are significant).
- There are latest amendments or updates to strengthen the protection and promotion of Pakistan's heritage culture (within Sindh) within the legal infrastructure as $MV= 3.26$ ($MV>TV$) at $t= 3.156$ (findings are significant). This project/ study paved the way to facilitate new amendments within Sindh via a signed MoU between Creative Commons, Pakistan Chapter and Ministry of Culture, Govt. of Sindh.
- There are significant incentives or mechanisms within the legal framework to encourage private sector participation in heritage culture preservation projects, as $MV= 3.32$ ($MV>TV$) at $t= 3.787$ (findings are significant).
- Ministry of Culture ensures significantly that the legal infrastructure adapts to new challenges and opportunities in heritage culture preservation as $MV= 3.22$ ($MV>TV$) at $t= 2.507$ (findings are significant).
- The channels are available for reporting violations or seeking assistance related to heritage culture preservation under the existing legal framework as $MV= 3.41$ ($MV>TV$) at $t= 4.931$ (findings are significant).
- The Ministry of Culture significantly collaborates with international organizations and other countries to exchange knowledge in the legal infrastructure for heritage culture, as $MV= 3.52$ ($MV>TV$) at $t= 5.996$ (findings are significant).

This project further deployed Kendall's correlation and OLS tests to evaluate the nexus between several proxies of legal frameworks. The findings of Kendall's correlation test and OLS explored that:

- The legal frameworks and regulations which are in place to safeguard and protect the diverse heritage culture of Pakistan is 15.5% significantly positively associated with the national collaborations that Ministry of Culture has with other government bodies for enforcing heritage culture preservation laws effectively at $p= 0.005<0.05$ (findings are significant).
- The legal frameworks and regulations which are in place to safeguard and protect the diverse heritage culture of Pakistan, 16.8% significantly positively impacts the national collaborations that the Ministry of Culture does with other government bodies to enforce heritage culture preservation laws effectively at $p= 0.005<0.05$ (findings are significant).
- The presence of legal frameworks and regulations to safeguard and protect the diverse heritage culture of Pakistan is neither significantly associated with the rest of proxies of legal frameworks nor impacts them that include 1. The latest amendments or updates to strengthen the protection and promotion of Pakistan's heritage culture within the legal infrastructure, 2. The incentives or mechanisms within the legal framework to encourage private sector participation in heritage culture preservation projects, 3. Assurance from the Ministry of Culture that the legal infrastructure adapts to new challenges and opportunities in heritage culture preservation, 4. The availability of channels for reporting violations or seeking assistance related to heritage culture preservation

under the existing legal framework and 5. The international collaboration Ministry of Culture does, to exchange knowledge in the legal infrastructure for heritage culture.

D. Key links of the Project

For addressing all three mentioned Infrastructures of GLAMs/ open GLAMs/ Heritage, the XploreOpen platform has been established for connecting the Heritage and GLAM community and other allied stakeholders with each other. XploreOpen's website, dashboard, padlet mapping of all local heritage sites and the social media accounts are developed which are the key deliveries of this project along with the empirical findings to conclude the heritage science of Pakistani heritage.

- A. www.xploreopen.org
- B. <https://xploreopen.org/open-glams-heritage>
- C. <https://twitter.com/xploreopen>
- D. <https://www.facebook.com/exploreopen/>
- E. <https://padlet.com/ccpakchap/glams-pakistan-e6zwd2c5a1yphgft>
- F. <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/18D-BKGcwwzq5kvVokVsfOCBXVV3luzxc/edit#gid=81061386>

E. Discussion & Conclusion:

This comprehensive initiative has not only quantified and assessed the existing GLAMs and heritage sites in Pakistan but also laid the groundwork for a sustainable and open approach to heritage science. The amalgamation of legal, technological, and social infrastructures, coupled with innovative mapping solutions, signifies a significant leap towards preserving and sharing Pakistan's diverse cultural heritage. The journey continues as the project looks ahead to further developments and advancements in the realm of Open heritage and GLAMs.

Project budget reporting (outline your costs and indicate if you spent all the money allocated by CC to your project)

The incurred expenses are detailed as follows:

1. Traveling Cost: \$1000.00 in US Dollars for visiting the country's heritage sites and GLAMs (Given that this project encompasses all major GLAMs in Pakistan, along with the country's significant heritage sites).
2. Cost of the Web-based Platform and Technical Support for developments of website and dashboard (social and technical infrastructure): \$1500.00 in US Dollars (This covers the development and maintenance costs of the user-friendly open heritage platform/ dashboard, and website).
3. Incentives for Investigators, Experts & Contributors: \$1500.00 in US Dollars (Expert Investigators: Dr. Subhani & Amber Osman from CC Pakistan Chapter (Founder & Co-founder of XploreOpen), two technical coordinators (Samair Nazeer & Monis Arifeen khan), and ten other contributors/ volunteers including Muhammad Babar Siddiqi, Syed Muhammad Haris Abidi, Hafiz Hamza Khan, Sidra Naz, Abdul Basit, Yasir Hussain, Rubaish Irfan, Aadrish Mushtaq, Sehrish Mushtaq and Bilal Sheikh from ILMA University, Pakistan).

P.S.: It is noteworthy that 100% of the funds, allocated i.e. \$4000.00 USD, have been fully utilized to complete this project.

Attachments - share with us any media releases, videos, blog posts, tweets, or other published materials so CC can promote your project and the outcomes

The published Web link on the main outcomes of the project.

<https://xploreopen.org/open-glams-heritage/>

Further, the media release and Blog post at DOAJ platform, will be submitted separately once the blog is published.

Feedback on the Open Culture Platform Activity Fund process, the documentation, this form, or anything else with regards to the process you would like to share with us (internal feedback, not for public distribution)

The chance offered by the Open Culture Platform Activity Fund to individuals and organizations to realize cultural projects is truly valuable, nurturing creativity and community involvement. We express our gratitude for the fantastic initiative that is the Open Culture Platform Activity Fund and appreciate the straightforward participation process. Thank you for offering this platform to bolster and commemorate cultural pursuits within our community.

Intellectual Property: Grantee agrees that all original copyrighted material produced pursuant to this grant will be made available under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 international license or CC0 public domain dedication. Grantee assumes the burden and expense of clearing all third party rights associated with such material, including with respect to any materials received or maintained in confidence, and/or any third party rights, including but not limited to copyrights, trademarks, and rights of privacy and publicity.

Appendices:

1. Snapshot of Mapping of Open GLAMS & Heritage sites on Pakistan's map via Padlet

XploreOpen
CC BY SA

2. Copy of official MoU:

XploreOpen
CC BY SA

b. The Ministry of Culture, Govt. of Sindh commits to granting access to cultural resources and facilities, as appropriate, for collaborative undertakings.

c. Both Parties concur to allocate the requisite funding and resources to fulfill their respective commitments.

Financing and Resources:

Creative Commons Pakistan (Open GLAMS of Pakistan) pursue funding opportunities, grants, or donations to bolster collaborative projects, with financial responsibilities delineated in project-specific agreements.

Confidentiality:

Both Parties shall uphold the confidentiality of any sensitive information shared during the course of their cooperation.

Dispute Resolution:

Any disputes arising from this MOU shall be resolved through amicable negotiations between the Parties.

Termination:

Either Party may terminate this MOU by providing written notice to the other Party, subject to One Month notice period.

Governing Law:

This MOU shall be governed by and construed in accordance with the laws of Applicable Jurisdiction.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the undersigned Parties hereto have executed this MOU on the date first above mentioned.

For Creative Commons Pakistan (Open GLAMS of Pakistan):

Dr. Muhammad Imtiaz Subhani,
Lead of Creative Commons Pakistan Chapter
Creative Commons Pakistan Chapter
(Open GLAMS of Pakistan)

Date: 20-11-2023

For the Ministry of Culture

Mr. Abdul Aleem Lashari
Minister of Culture
Ministry of Culture, Govt. of
Sindh

Date: 20-11-23

XploreOpen
CC BY SA